

Reliability Engineering: A Demonstration of How Reliability Engineering Techniques and Methods Improve Processes, Products and Services

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Abstract— Understanding what, when and where to use the wide variety of reliability engineering tools available helps in achieving the highest reliability in products, processes and services. This paper outlines the value of using Weibull Analysis, Reliability Block Diagrams Reliability Centered Maintenance and Root Cause Analysis and as techniques for processes, products, equipment and services improvement. Reliability Engineering tools help to determine the relationship between the process and the equipment. A demonstration of where and how the reliability engineering techniques can be applied is shown in the research. Every product and process design and their development are unique such that meticulous planning is required to map the reliability tasks to the identified constraints. A product with complex multidisciplinary integrated functions requires efficient reliability tools. These tools are required to be used to assess built-in safety and reliability features of the product under an applicable environment. The techniques discussed in this research will help in determining the present and future reliability of the products or processes.

Keywords—Reliability engineering, reliability, availability, maintainability, meantime to repair (MTTR), mean time between failures (MTBF).

I. INTRODUCTION

THE safe and reliable operation of technical systems is of great significance for the protection of human life and health, the environment, and the economy in general [1]. Reliability engineering is engineering that emphasizes dependability in the life cycle management of a product. Dependability describes the ability of a system or component to function under stated conditions for a specific period of time. Manufacturing system is a vital factor in ensuring product quality and productivity in a production process [2]. Before any reliability analyses can be carried out on a system, there must be knowledge of the operational relationships of the various elements comprising that system. The reliability of a system cannot be improved or even evaluated unless there is a thorough understanding of how each of its elements function and how these functions affect systems operation. A

demonstration of where and how the reliability engineering techniques can be applied is shown in the research.

II. RELIABILITY ENGINEERING TECHNIQUES

Reliability engineering can allow us to determine the relationship between the process and the equipment [3]. By using Weibull Analysis, Reliability Block Diagrams (RBD), Reliability Centered Maintenance (RCM) and Root cause Analysis (RCA) with cost and failure data, high level process problems can be linked to low level equipment failure modes.

III. WEIBULL ANALYSIS

In the 1930's Swedish Engineer and Mathematician Waloddi Weibull invented the Weibull formula for use in analyzing life failure data [3]. Weibull distribution is a flexible measurement that details the probable distribution associated with lifetime characteristics of a particular part or service component. Particularly focused on failure-rate, Weibull distribution is used throughout reliability engineering to anticipate and account for issues of wear-out during development [4]. The importance of Weibull is that it allows the analyst to draw relatively good inferences with a small number of data points. The three Weibull parameters of particular interest are alpha (α), beta (β), and gamma (γ). Alpha represents the characteristic life of a component, or the point where 63.2% of the items in service will have failed [3].

$$\alpha = \frac{\text{mean} - L}{\gamma \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right)} \quad [1]$$

Gamma represents the beginning of each phase of the bathtub curve shown in fig 2.1. Beta is the shape factor and represents whether the analyzed failures are displaying infant failure, random failure, or wear out failure characteristics. The Location (L) parameter is the lower bound for the variable. The Shape parameter is a number greater than 0, usually a small number less than 10. The ability to interpret these three parameters allows us to set appropriate maintenance strategies based on the failure mechanisms that are present.

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Fig 2.1 Bathtub Curve [5]

A. Use of Weibull analysis

In most organizations, the life distribution of equipment and their components, and analysis of the utilizations at failure and the current utilization for all non-failed components failure data and equipment life span will not be available [6]. Their data will at best be of some representative sample of the failures which have occurred, and of utilization of unfailed units. It cannot be stressed too highly, though, that life of unfailed units must be known if a realistic estimate of lifetimes to failure is to be made, and therefore, data must be collected on unfailed units in the sample.

The basic elements in defect data analysis comprise:

- A population, from which some sample is taken in the form of times to failure.
- An analytical technique, Weibull in this case, which is then applied to the sample of failure data to derive a mathematical model for the behavior of the sample, and hopefully of the population also, and finally
- Some deductions which are generated by an examination of the model.

Weibull analysis requires times to failure. This is higher quality data than knowledge of the number of failures in an interval. A failure must be a defined event and preferably objective rather than some subjectively assessed degradation in performance [6]. A typical sample, therefore, might at its most superficial level comprise a collection of individual times to failure for the equipment under investigation. One simple method to perform a Weibull analysis is by calculating median-rank plotting positions via a simple formula and then plotting the cumulative percentage of devices that have failed versus their failure times on Weibull probability paper. If the data falls on a straight line, as it often does, the Weibull distribution parameters can be easily estimated based on the plot. An even easier approach is to use one of the many software packages available.

The ability of the Weibull distribution to model failure situations of many types, including those where non-constant hazard conditions apply, make it one of the most generally

useful distributions for analyzing failure data [7]. The information it provides, both in terms of the modelled distribution of times to failure and the prevailing failure regime is fundamental to the selection of a successful maintenance strategy, whether or not component life is an element in that strategy

IV. RELIABILITY BLOCK DIAGRAMS (RBDS)

A Reliability Block Diagram is a diagrammatic method for showing how component reliability contributes to the success or failure of a complex system. A Reliability Block Diagram models a system as a collection of blocks representing the systems logical or physical component [8]. The often used models include series, parallel and hybrid models [9]. The models are represented by figs 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 respectively. If part X breaks down, the whole system will be down if the components are connected in series as shown in fig 2.2. However if two part X's are placed in parallel then if one fails the other will take the full load, and hence the availability and reliability of the system as a whole will increase.

Fig 2.2: Availability in series.

Fig 2.3: Availability in Parallel

Fig 2.4: An example of a hybrid reliability block diagram [10].

In fig 2.4 the system is available if and only if subsystem A, at least one of subsystems B1 or B2 and subsystem C are available. For complex system's RBD's make the reliability of a system easy to understand, expose weakness much quicker, and make what if analysis much easier [10]. Used early in a design cycle it allocates reliability among blocks, guiding architecture and decisions to achieve an overall system reliability requirements. Given the availability functions of the individual blocks, the total availability of the system can be calculated directly or through the Monte-Carlo simulation. Analysis of RBD's also makes it possible to calculate the contribution of each individual component downtime of the entire system and to quickly analyze the sensitivity of changes to the reliability of the complete system on the overall availability of the system.

V. RELIABILITY CENTERED MAINTENANCE (RCM)

The main objective of reliability centered maintenance is the cost effective maintenance of the plant components' inherent reliability value [11]. RCM philosophy employs preventive maintenance (PM), predictive maintenance (PdM), real time monitoring (RTM), run-to-fail (RTF) and proactive maintenance techniques in an integrated manner to increase the probability that a machine or component will function in the required manner over its design life cycle with a minimum maintenance [12]. RCM uses the concept of Failure Modes, Effects and Criticality Analysis (FMECA) to determine what can go wrong with critical assets [13]. Although there is a great deal of variation in the application of RCM, most procedures include seven steps stated below:

1. Prepare the analysis.
2. Select the equipment to be analyzed.
3. Identify the function.
4. Identify the functional failures.
5. Identify and evaluate (categorize) the effects of failure.
6. Identify the cause of failure.
7. Select maintenance tasks.

If these steps were to be grouped into 3 major blocks these blocks will be:

- Define (Steps 1, 2 and 3)
- Analyze (steps 4, 5 and 6)
- Act (Step 7)

Prior to the development of the RCM methodology, it was widely believed that everything had a right time for some form of preventive maintenance (PM), usually a replacement or an overhaul [14]. An example of the application of RCM was carried out by some airline companies who had observed that PM did not always reduce the probability of failure and that some items did not seem to benefit in any way from PM. These companies formed a task force to study the subject of preventive maintenance. The results of the study confirmed that PM was effective only for items having a certain pattern of failures. The study also concluded that PM should be required only when assurance of safe operation is required. Otherwise, the decision to do or not do PM should be based on economics. The RCM approach provides a logical way of determining if PM makes sense for a given item and if so selecting the appropriate type of PM [14]. RCM seeks to preserve system or equipment function, not just operability for operability's sake. The failure characteristics of the item in question must be understood to determine the efficacy of PM. RCM is not overly concerned with simple failure rates, it seeks to know the conditional probability of failure at specific ages (the probability that failure will occur in each given operating bracket). By implementing RCM it can be deduced that all items benefit from PM. Moreover even when PM would have

be effective, it is often less expensive to allow the item to run to fail rather do PM. The benefits of RCM include reduced costs and increased availability.

VI. ROOT CAUSE ANALYSIS

The objective of root cause analysis is to identify "root causes" so that these latent failures will be eliminated or modified and future occurrences of similar problems or mishaps may be prevented. If root cause failure analysis is not performed analyst only identifies and fixes the proximate causes then the underlying causes may continue to produce similar problems or mishaps in the same or related areas [15]. As an example, quality control of company X issued a non-conformance for brass tube sheet. The non-conformance was issued due to an incorrect hole pattern i.e. 34 hole pattern was drilled where a 36 hole pattern was required. The cause of the incorrect hole pattern was a combination of engineering oversight and no quality check performed by the machinist. At first the blame was put on the CNC drill operator who drilled the 34 holes instead of the 36 holes. After performing Root cause root analysis, it was discovered that the incorrect hole pattern was caused by engineering oversight and no quality check from the drill operator after spot drilling. Engineering provided the CNC operator with a design used one month prior for the same customer. Engineering was not aware the hole pattern was different. Also engineering used previous programs/design to reduce design costs to the customer. The CNC operator only checked spot drilling for hole location and uniformity. It is not typical for CNC drill operator to check the hole location against the blueprint during this stage in production and the operator assumed the program provided from engineering was correct.

After applying RCA company X recommended that:

- i. Standard operation procedure must be implanted to verify hole location with drawings and engineering.
- ii. Quality control checks should be done after spot drilling, with engineering, design and customer request. There will be a slight increase in costs associated with production.

A. Fishbone analysis

The fishbone analysis is a tool for analyzing the business process and its effectiveness. It is defined as a fishbone because of its structural outlook and appearance. In normal stature it looks like a skeleton of a fish. The fishbone diagram and analysis typically evaluates the causes and sub-causes of one particular problem and therefore assists to uncover all the symptoms of any business problem [16]. For that particular reason it is also termed as "Cause-Effect analysis".

Fig 2.5: Fishbone diagram

In the fishbone diagram shown in fig 2.5 the main problem which occurred has been put on the head of the diagram and the causes are put as the bones and then smaller bones are created as sub-causes. Ultimately after completion of the diagram it is a comprehensive evaluation of the causes of the main problems and also reveals the root causes as of the problem [16].

B. Importance of Root Cause Analysis

Root Cause Analysis (RCA) is a popular and often-used technique that helps people answer the question of why the problem occurred in the first place [17]. Root Cause Analysis seeks to identify the origin of a problem. It uses a specific set of steps, with associated tools, to find the primary cause of the problem, so that you can:

1. Determine what happened.
2. Determine why it happened.
3. Figure out what to do to reduce the likelihood that it will happen again.

RCA assumes that systems and events are interrelated. An action in one area triggers an action in another, and another, and so on. By tracing back these actions, you can discover where the problem started and how it grew into the symptom you're now facing.

There are usually three basic types of causes:

1. Physical causes – Tangible, material items failed in some way (for example, a car's brakes stopped working).
2. Human causes – People did something wrong, or did not do something that was needed. Human causes typically lead to physical causes (for example, no one filled the brake fluid, which led to the brakes failing).

3. Organizational causes – A system, process, or policy that people use to make decisions or do their work is faulty (for example, no one person was responsible for vehicle maintenance, and everyone assumed someone else had filled the brake fluid).

Root Cause Analysis looks at all three types of causes. It involves investigating the patterns of negative effects, finding hidden flaws in the system, and discovering specific actions that contributed to the problem. This often means that RCA reveals more than one root cause.

VII. CONCLUSION

Reliability Engineering tools such as Weibull Analysis, Reliability Block Diagrams, RCM, and RCA are useful for solving equipment and process/system problems. The tools can be used at a high level to give an overall picture of where the majority of problems lie. Once the value of gains is identified the tools can be used to dig deeper into the issues to find and eliminate the root causes of both process/system and equipment related problems.

VIII. RECOMMENDATION

It is recommended that these reliability techniques are best used with the help of various computerized modelling techniques available so as to get more accurate results in a short period of time.

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